

ISSN 2181-2357

XALQARO NAZARIY VA AMALIY TADQIQOTLAR
JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

JURNAL FARG'ONA POLITEXNIKA
INSTITUTI HAMKORLIGIDA NASHR
ETILADI

VOLUME 3,
Issue 1
2023

«Al-Ferganus» MChJ.

A. M. Abdullayev

«Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali»

Ilmiy jurnal.

2021 yil noyabrdan beri nashr etilmoqda.

Oyiga bir marta nashr etiladi. 16+

3-tom, 1 -son.

Yanvar 2023 y.

Tahririyat kengashi raisi Salomov O'ktam Raximovich, FarPI rektori

Bosh muharrir K. I. Kurpayanidi

Tahririyat hay'ati: A.M.Abdullaev, M.S.Ashurov, E.A.Mo'minova, K.X.Abduraxmonov, A.N.Asaul, A.V.Burkov, U.V.G'ofurov, M.A.Ikromov, D.Kudbiev, E.S.Margianiti, B.Obrenovich, L.NA Sultonov, L.NA. , A.Xasanov, Sh.T.Karimov, Sh.Sh.Salixanova, U.K.Alimov, S.M.Turabdjano, B.A.Alimatov, R.J.Tozhiyev, A.A.Risqulov, B.M.Tursunov, S. F. Ergashev, J.D.Axmedov, Kh.A. Akramov, M.X. Xakimov, Sh.M. Iskandarova, Z.M. Sobirova, A.M. Muxtarova, L.M. Babakhodjaeva..

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IF(Impact Factor) **9.88 /2022**
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Ro'yxatga olish № 1189 Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021.

Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar bazalariga kiritilgan.

Impact-faktor 2021 Evaluation Pending

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Jurnal jahon va mintaqaviy darajada fan va amaliyotning rivojlanish masalalariga bag'ishlangan.

Jurnal olimlar, o'qituvchilar, doktorantlar, talabalar uchun mo'ljallangan.

Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali.

2023. T.3. №1.

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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«Al-Ferganus» LLC.
A. M. Abdullaev
“International journal of theoretical and practical research”
Scientific Journal.
Published since November 2021.
Schedule: monthly. 16+

Volume 3, Issue 1

January, 2023.

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IF(Impact Factor) **9.88 / 2022**

<http://journalseeker.research>

bib.com/view/issn/2181-2357

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2023: 5,971

<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

Registered with the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Registration No. 1189 dated 17-06-2021.

The journal "International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research" is included Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Impact-factor 2021 Evaluation Pending

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

The Journal addresses issues of global and regional Science and Practice. For scientists, teachers, doctoral students, students.

(2022). International journal of theoretical and practical research, 3(1).

ISSN 2181-2357

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«Al-Ferganus» ООО.

А. М. Абдуллаев

«Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований»

Научный журнал.

Издается с ноября 2021 г.

Выходит один раз в месяц. 16+

Том 3, Номер 1.

Январь 2023 г.

Председатель редакционного совета Саломов Уктам Рахимович, ректор ФерПИ

Главный редактор К. И. Курпаяниди

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Адрес редакции: 150107

г. Фергана, ул. Ферганская, 86

Тел. +998971003888

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E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **9.88 /2022**

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Зарегистрирован в Агентстве информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации

Президента Республики Узбекистан.

Регистрации № 1189 от 17-06-2021.

Журнал «Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований» включен в Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Импакт-факторы журнала: 2021 Evaluation Pending

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В журнале рассматриваются вопросы развития мировой и региональной науки и практики. Для ученых, преподавателей, докторантов, студентов.

Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований. 2023. Т. 3. №1.

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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2023, Фергана, Узбекистан

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QR CODE of this issue of the magazine

<https://dx.doi.org/>

qo'llab-quvvatlash sohasida raqamli ta'limning zamonaviy metodlarini qo'llab-quvvatlashi, innovatsion xizmatlarni samarali tartibga solish normalarini ishlab chiqishi, yangi bozorlarni o'zlashtirishda ko'maklashishi hamda texnologik jarayonlarning chuqurlashuvida yuzaga chiqadigan havflarni pasaytirish choralarini ko'rishi maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati:

1. "Raqamli iqtisodiyot va elektron hukumatni keng joriy etish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PQ-4699 son qarori, 2020 yil 28-aprel. *Qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi*, 29.04.2020-y.,
2. Sharipov, F. F., Krotenko, T. Y., & Dyakonova, M. A. (2020, April). Talent management: needs and prospects for business development in the digital economy. In *International Online Forum named after A. Ya. Kibanov" Innovative Personnel Management"* (pp. 514-518). Springer, Cham.
3. Barsukov, D., Kuzmina, S., Morozova, N., & Pimenova, A. (2018). Professional education for digital economy: trends and prospects. In *MATEC Web of Conferences (Vol. 170, p. 01063)*. EDP Sciences.
4. Khamidov, O. K., & Kahhorov, O. S. (2020). Prospects of monitoring graduates' employment in digital technologies. *Scientific Reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(5), 268-273.
5. Kurpayanidi, K. (2021). National innovation system as a key factor in the sustainable development of the economy of Uzbekistan. In *E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 258, p. 05026)*. EDP Sciences.
6. Bobobekov, S. (2021). Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining o'quv jarayonida elektron ta'lim muhitini yaratish. *Журнал математики и информатики*, 1(4).

Kardo Sabah Abdullah

master's degree student,

Matveeva Valeria Pavlovna

master's degree student,

Supervisor: Matveeva Yulia Valerevna,

Associate Professor, Samara National Research University, Institute of Economics and Management, Samara, Russia

Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7595457>

THE ROLE AND IMPACT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON THE BANKING INDUSTRY

Кардо Сабах Абдуллах

студент магистратуры,

Матвеева Валерия Павловна

студент магистратуры,

Матвеева Юлия Валерьевна

*доцент Самарский национальный исследовательский университет,
Институт экономики и управления, г. Самара, Россия.*

РОЛЬ И ВЛИЯНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА БАНКОВСКУЮ ОТРАСЛЬ

The rapid progress in information and communication technology has had a radical impact on the financial sector in general and the banking sector in particular over the past decades, and it has now become a very important tool with strategic benefits for banks that achieve progress, success and provide better quality in banking services provided to customers, where technology is one of the important pillars. In financial and banking dealings, it also contributes mainly to international business operations, which had a significant impact on the growth of the global economy.

The banking sector is one of the first sectors that benefited from the technological revolution and its multiple uses in the financial fields, which began in the fifties of the last century, followed by the installation of the first ATM, which was introduced in the United States of America in 1968. The emergence of ATMs at that time had a great impact on improving service and convenience for customers, in addition to reducing costs. Although ATMs were limited to cash withdrawal service, now they provide many services from account inquiries and transfer money between the required accounts and many other banking services. For example, there are now scanning machines that enable banks and customers to accept cash or checks, as there are many banks in different parts of the world that use technology in advanced applications such as interviewing, granting and implementing customer loans and allowing face-to-face discussion with the bank service representative via video anywhere, which greatly enriches the direct interaction between bank employees and customers. And thus shorten the distances through communication and save time and effort for all relevant parties.

Information technology has helped banks to rise quickly, which led to significant gains for the banking sector. Modern technological innovations have had a great impact on the speedy processing and sending of information, the ease of marketing banking products and improving their image, in addition to the ability to deliver service and information faster to customers and anywhere in the world. The world, which also helped in the interactive information networks and on a larger scale in an unprecedented way, it is the development that changed the schedule of all banks' products and the way they are presented, and developed their products and the type of banking services provided.

It is worth noting that most banks are making great efforts to keep pace with these modern and advanced systems and innovative and new banking operations, as we find that the development of information and communication technology has given banks a great opportunity to provide the most diverse and convenient financial services without adding new branches.

As for the development of Internet services and the use of networks in banks, it has an effective relationship and has a radical impact with the banking sector in general. The

uses are wide-ranging, low-cost and convenient for the financial network of banks as a whole. It has clearly facilitated banking services anywhere and at any time for customers, in addition to that many Some of the banks have improved the telecommunications network, such as using a landline or mobile phone to complete banking operations, which should be carried out on the Internet, which in turn leads to the integration of e-commerce and Internet banking with banks to gradually replace manual work and personal attendance by the customer to the bank.

The banking sector in Jordan believes in technology and its ability to help banks launch and transform quickly. The use of information technology on a large scale in Jordan began with the introduction of the first ATMs, where the introduction of ATMs had a positive impact on the performance of Jordanian banks, in addition to communication technology, which helped banks to speed up Perform operations and reduce cost through the use of advanced digital devices and electronic computers that reduce the number of employees used and increase profits in addition to many benefits such as ease of dealing and outsourcing with financial institutions around the world and improving service where information and communication technology had a significant impact on outsourcing For financial services with reduced costs, as there were pioneering initiatives by the Bank for my global central bank to prevent losses, develop plans for the continuity of banking business and mitigate operational risks, which mainly stem from the complex and intertwined banking business on the electronic and human levels in different banks, knowing that mitigating operational risks for banks It mainly extends to developing plans and strategies for business continuity for banks with a focus on the essence of banking solutions and support systems that help recovery after disasters because the risks facing the banking industry have increased a lot as is noticeable due to the large size and diversity of uses of technology in banks and therefore the risk of systems failure will be greater And the worst impact on banks, realizing that the fact that “hackers” entered any system, whether it was used by private or governmental banking institutions, gave great importance to the presence of protection in computer systems, which is an important part of the operational risks of various institutions.

Banking institutions have a certain behavior that depends directly on technological and technical support to monitor markets, customers and investors. It is important for banks to disclose appropriate financial conditions in accordance with the accounting methods used, including international standards such as IAS 32, 39 and international financial reporting standards such as Standard No. 7 Moreover, banks should enhance the processes of introducing improvements to information by the risk management in different banks according to the Basel II agreement. Within this framework, there will be requirements, the most important of which are the advanced infrastructure and technological transformation in banks, in order to move towards the advanced approach within the framework of the second Basel agreement on the one hand. "Data storage" in addition to the application of advanced programs to deal with customers, so all of these things depend, as we have seen, on technology mainly in order to move forward towards the future.

Therefore, there is a strong and reciprocal relationship between the advanced technology on the one hand and the legal framework and regulatory policy on the other

hand for the bank, as this is very important for establishing the efficiency and stability of the banking system. It is necessary to mention here the Electronic Transactions Law and the Anti-fraud Law, where it has become possible to use electronic transactions and punish fraud and fraud, in addition to monitoring activities related to electronic card operations. The intention of these laws is to create the regulatory framework for banks and financial institutions to use information technology facilities to carry out their operations and mitigate the risks that can They arise from the misuse of systems and tools.

Conclusions The world witnessed during the past years, and continues to witness a very rapid development in the forms of information technology that it had an impact on economic activity, and during the second half of the 1990s a group of people appeared terms that refer to the role of information technology in economic activity, such as the term knowledge economy and the information economy, as this development encompassed all areas of life, especially the banks that are experiencing challenges huge in the last two decades of the last two decades of the last century and the beginning of the current century, they became the banks it operates in a changing environment under the influence of several factors, including information technology.

The client has become more familiar with information technology, which has changed the size of his aspirations for the services he provides, it has the bank, which has led to its increasing interest in electronic services, as the customer wants to obtain services At the place and time he wants and through the means he chooses, which necessitated the banks to integrate information technology in its daily business, as this helped it to 77 benefit from it and develop it not only to raise the quality of banking services rather, it is a source of many new banking services, and that is why traditional banks have tended to create electronic banking services that suit the needs and demands of their customers on the one hand, and to achieve profit for the bank.

References:

1. Abdel-Khaleq, Muhammad, Financial and Banking Administration, Dar Osama for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan. 9090
2. Alyan, Ribhi Mustafa, Foundations of Contemporary Marketing, Dar Al-Safa Publishing and Distribution, 9th edition, Amman, Jordan, 9090
3. Fathi, Amer Ibrahim, Alaa El Din Abdel Qader Al Janabi, Management Information Systems, Publishing House Distribution and Printing, 03th Edition, Amman, 90
4. Kandelji, Amer Ibrahim, Iman Fadel Al-Samarrai, Information Technology and its Applications, Foundation Al-Waraq for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan, 90
5. Curtel, Farid, Marketing of Services, Dar Kunouz Al-Maarifa Al-Ilmia Publishing, Amman, 90
6. Mustafa, his father, Roy Kamal El-Din, Mohamed Samir Kamel, Accounting Information Systems, University House Publishing, Egypt, 90
7. Mualla, Naji, The Origins of Banking Marketing, Dar Al-Safa Publishing, Lebanon, 9114

8. Yassin, Saad Ghaleb, Fundamentals of Management Information Systems and Information Technology, Dar Al-Mahraj, Amman, Jordan, 9002

9. Yassin, Saad Ghaleb, Fundamentals of Management Information Systems and Information Technology, Dar Al-Mahraj Publishing and Distribution, Amman, 900

10. Institute of Banking Studies, Electronic Banking Services, Illuminations Magazine, Issue 99 Kuwait, 909.

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ЭЪЛОН

Хурматли ҳамкасабалар “Al-Ferganus” нашриёти ва “Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” электрон журнали Ўзбекистон таълим хизматлари бозорида ўзининг фаолиятини бошлаганлигини маълум қиламиз.

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Это прекрасная возможность одним из первых опубликовать свои научные публикации. Наше издательство «AL-FARGANUS» предоставляет услуги по прикреплению международных цифровых идентификаторов ISBN, Doi к учебникам, учебным пособиям, монографиям и научным брошюрам, созданию электронных макетов их обложек и дизайнов в современной электронной форме, размещению опубликованных работ в электронные публикации.

Отличие нашего издательства от других издательств в том, что мы предоставляем быстрые и качественные услуги, а главное, бесплатно размещаем ваши работы в Национальной библиотеке Узбекистана им. Алишера Навои и оказываем помощь в размещении вашей работы в Российской национальной библиотеке, а также на платформе Российского индекса научного цитирования (РИНЦ, e-library) облегчить размещение.

Совместно с Ферганским политехническим институтом запущен проект электронного научного журнала «Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali – International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research. Международный журнал теоретических и прикладных исследований».

Миссия научного электронного журнала направлена на развитие национальной и зарубежной науки, обеспечение общедоступности теоретических

позиций и практических результатов прикладных исследований. В журнале представлены следующие специальности Высшей аттестационной комиссии Республики Узбекистан по физике и математике, химии, биологии, геологии и минералогии, технике, сельскому хозяйству, истории, экономике, философии, филологии, географии, праву, педагогике, медицине, архитектуре, психологии, социологии. Журнал публикует научные статьи отечественных и зарубежных авторов о достижениях и перспективах науки, результатах научных исследований ученых, проводящих исследования. Электронный журнал издается один раз в месяц.

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Электронный адрес: Alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

Наш адрес в телеграмм: @Alferganus_ltd

Телефоны: (97) 100-38-88

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PUBLIC IDENTIFIERS OF INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

PUBLISHER: AL-FERGANUS LLC - UZBEKISTAN

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ADDRESS^{IJA}

IJA.ZONE/16456457645

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IJA}

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH^{IAA}

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi

№ 7430-3360-d0e2-4e5b-8cf1-9914-2923
Hujjat yaratilgan sana: 2021-06-22
Ariza raqami: 32087634

Hujjat berilgan: ОБЩЕСТВО С ОГРАНИЧЕННОЙ
ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТЬЮ "AL-FERGANUS"
Qabul qiluvchining identifikatsiya raqami: 308291417

Ommaviy axborot vositasi davlat ro'yxatidan o'tkazilganligi to'g'risida
GUVOHNOMA

№ 1189

Nomi: "Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar"

Tarqatish shakli: jurnal

Til(lar)i: o'zbek, rus, ingliz

Muassis(lar)i: "AL-FERGANUS" mas'uliyati cheklangan jamiyat

Ixtisoslashuvi: fan sohalaridagi ilmiy nashr

Tahririyat manzili: 150100, Farg'ona viloyati, Farg'ona shahar, Mustaqillik ko'chasi, 42-uy

Tarqatish hududi: O'zbekiston Respublikasi hamda belgilangan tartibda chet davlatlarga

Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021

Ro'yxatdan o'tkazuvchi organ rahbari: Xodjayev Asadjon Azatbekovich

Mazkur hujjat Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017 yil 15 sentyabrdagi 728-son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Yagona interaktiv davlat xizmatlari portali to'g'risidagi nizomga muvofiq shakllantirilgan elektron hujjatning nusxasi hisoblanadi. Elektron hujjatning nusxasida ko'rsatilgan ma'lumotlar to'g'riligini tekshirish uchun repo.gov.uz veb-saytiga o'ting va elektron hujjatning noyob raqamini kiriting yoki mobil telefon yordamida QR-kodni skaner qiling. Diqqat! Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017 yil 15 sentyabrdagi 728-son qaroriga muvofiq elektron hujjatlardagi ma'lumotlar qonuniy hisoblanadi. Davlat organlariga Yagona portalda shakllantirilgan elektron hujjatlarning nusxalarini qabul qilishni rad etishlari qat'iyan taqiqlangan.

9103

21.03.2021

Центр государственных услуг

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Общество с ограниченной ответственностью

Местонахождение:

Ферганская область, г. Фергана, Aeroport,

Свидетельство выдано:

Ферганская область, г. Фергана, ЦЕНТР
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